

Full genome sequence of *Bacillus velezensis* B38 strain isolated from soil in Tunisia.

Malek GHARBI^{1,2}, Manel CHAOUACHI¹, Dorra GHARBI¹, Ines KARKOUCH¹, Nadia FARES¹, Olfà TABBENE^{1*}

¹ Laboratory of Bioactive Substances, Centre of Biotechnology of Borj Cedria, BP 901, Hammam-Lif, 2050, Tunisia.

² Faculty of science of Tunis, University of Tunis Manar, University Campus Farhat Hached, BP-94 Rommana, 1068 Tunis, Tunisia

* Corresponding authors: tabb_olfa@yahoo.fr

Abstract

This study presents the genomic analysis of a novel *Bacillus velezensis* strain, isolated from Maroccan soil, based on whole-genome sequencing. The strain demonstrated strong antimicrobial activity against a broad spectrum of pathogenic bacteria, fungi, and yeasts. Whole-genome sequencing provides a comprehensive approach to characterize this strain and offers deeper insights into its antimicrobial mechanisms.

Introduction

Gram-positive *Bacillus* species are ubiquitous microorganisms widely distributed in diverse environments, including soil and food matrices, and have garnered significant attention for their potential probiotic applications (Lyng and Kovács., 2023). These bacteria are well known for their remarkable biosynthetic capacities, producing a diverse array of bioactive compounds, including ribosomal and non-ribosomal peptides, volatile organic compounds, polyketides, and hybrid molecules combining polyketide and non-ribosomal peptide structures (Caulier et al., 2019). These secondary metabolites exhibit potent antimicrobial properties, enabling *Bacillus* species to inhibit a broad spectrum of pathogenic bacteria (Huarachi et al., 2022), fungi (Yuan et al. 2012), and yeasts (Tabbene et al., 2011). The advent of whole-genome sequencing (WGS) has revolutionized microbial research, offering a powerful tool for in-depth

characterization of bacterial strains at the genomic level (Chukamnerd et al., 2023). WGS provides critical insights into the genetic basis of antimicrobial activity, shedding light on biosynthetic gene clusters responsible for the production of bioactive compounds (Hafeez et al., 2023). Additionally, genomic analysis facilitates the assessment of strain safety, identifying genes associated with potential pathogenicity or antibiotic resistance (Zaghloul and El Halfawy., 2022). The comprehensive genetic profiling not only enhances our understanding of antimicrobial mechanisms but also paves the way for the biotechnological application of *Bacillus* strains in medicine, agriculture, and food preservation (Akinsemolu et al., 2024). Furthermore, genomic exploration may lead to the discovery of novel antimicrobial compounds, addressing the growing demand for alternative strategies to combat antibiotic-resistant pathogens (Hafeez et al., 2023). Hence, the present study outlined the whole-genome sequence of the *Bacillus* strain B38, producing diverse lipopeptides and exhibiting potent antimicrobial activity against a broad spectrum of microbial pathogens. Genomic analysis aims to identify the biosynthetic gene clusters responsible for the production of diverse lipopeptide compounds, providing valuable insights into the strain's antimicrobial mechanisms and potential biotechnological applications.

Material and Methods

Isolation of the bacterial stain from soil

Bacillus strain B38 was isolated from soil samples using a serial dilution technique. Briefly, 10 g of soil was suspended in 90 mL of sterile physiological saline 0.9% and allowed to settle for 2 h. The suspension was then serially diluted (10^{-1} to 10^{-4}) in saline buffer (0.9 % NaCl), and aliquots from each dilution were streaked onto tryptic soy broth (TSB) agar plates. The plates were incubated at 30°C for 24 h. Single colonies were selected and subjected to successive streak purification on TSB agar plates to obtain pure isolates. The purified strain was maintained at -80 °C in TSB broth supplemented with 25% (v/v) glycerol for long time storage (Tabbene et al., 2009).

Sequencing of bacterial genomic DNA

Genomic DNA libraries of *Bacillus* strain B38 were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's protocol with some modifications. The input DNA was increased 2-fold, and PCR elongation time was increased to 45 seconds. DNA quantification and library preparation were carried out on a Hamilton Microlab STAR automated liquid handling system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland).

Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired end protocol. Reads were adapter trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality cutoff of Q15. De novo assembly was performed on samples using SPAdes version 3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and contigs were annotated using Prokka 1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Results

Genomic features

The whole genome sequencing of a *Bacillus* strain B38 was conducted. The sequence reads were assembled using Quast, yielding 39 contigs. The largest contig measured 1,126,375 base pairs, while the total genome assembly length for the strain B38 was 4,045,125 bp. The genomic G + C content of the strain B38 was determined to be 46,17%. The total number of genes, including protein-coding genes, tRNA genes, and rRNA genes is presented in Table 1. Based on Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) analysis and current taxonomic classification, the genome sequence of the strain B38 exhibited over 99% sequence identity with members of the *Bacillus* genus. The genome of the strain B38 exhibits high similarity to *B. velezensis*, suggesting its classification within this species.

Data availability

The whole-genome shotgun sequence of *Bacillus velezensis* strain B38 has been deposited in the DDBJ/ENA/GenBank database under the accession number JBAKJE000000000. Raw sequence reads are available in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under BioProject ID PRJNA1066102 and run number SRR27601939.

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We encourage and welcome feedback from the community. Please get in touch with TABBENE Olfa (tabb_olfa@yahoo.fr) for more information.

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Table 1. Summary Statistics for a Bioactive Molecule-Secreting Agent Assembled from Illumina Reads.

Bacterial strain	Biosample	Number of contigs (>=1000 bp)	largest contig	Total length	GC (%)	mean coverage	N50	CDS	tRNA	rRNA	GenBank accession (Assembly)	GenBank accession (reads)
<i>B. velezensis</i> B38	SAMN39481344	39	1,126,375	4,045,125	46,17	63,83	497,412	4,099	85	12	JBAKJE000000000	SRR27601939

